

MISCONCEPTIONS ABOUT THE NATURE OF RESEARCH AND THEIR REMEDIES

Dr. Rajeev Kumar*

Associate Professor, K. M. College of Education, Bhiwani, Haryana, India
rajeevkumarmce@gmail.com

Accepted: 05.05.2021

Published: 10.06.2021

Keywords: Information Analysis, Skilled Activity and Information Analysis.

Abstract

Research is a systematic process of collecting and analyzing information to increase our understanding of the phenomenon under study. It is the function of the researcher to contribute to the understanding of the phenomenon and to communicate that understanding to others. This article explains what research is, importance of research, how enjoyable it is to do research, etc.

Research is, however, a skilled activity. Like any skill, it must be practiced. The best way to improve your research method is, therefore, to continually assess your research practice against the objectives and guidelines.

problems by asking relevant questions and seeking answers to them. The role of research is to provide a method for obtaining those answers by inquiringly studying the evidence within the parameters of the scientific method.

The word “research” is used to cover a broad spectrum of meaning the activity, which makes it a decidedly confusing term for students. Unfortunately, many students have been having several misconceptions about the nature of research. On one hand, the word research connotes the finding of an item of information or the making of notes and the writing of a documented paper. On the other hand, it is used for the act of informing oneself about what one does not know or going through available sources to retrieve required information.

Paper Identification

*Corresponding Author

1 Meaning of Research

In every research area or subject, our knowledge is incomplete and problems are waiting to be solved. We address the void in our knowledge and those unresolved

2 The importance of research

The importance of research may vary according to kind, especially whether basic or applied.

i) Basic Research

Basic research aims to study an advance knowledge with no application to existing problems in view. The audience for basic research consists almost exclusively of other scholars or researchers interested in learning more about a phenomena. There is substantial basic

research is going on in subjects, like Physics, Chemistry, etc., whereas virtually no basic research being done in library science and only a small amount in information science.

ii) **Applied Research**

Applied research is designed to solve particular, existing problems so there is a much larger audience eager to support research that is likely to be profitable or solve problems of immediate concern.

Applied research can be very simplistic within a given application or it can become quite complicated. The principle of applied research is easy to understand, and does not require the same and complicated process of engaging in applied research.

Besides this, quite a bit of applied research is survey research or marketing research. This is the art and science of systematically asking questions and observing behaviour to obtain information from a population of interest.

3 **Need of research**

Following are the some of the reasons we undertake research has a profession or a hobby.

i) **Job oriented**

In most positions, some sort of research is required to support normal decision-making or Organizational growth.

The organizations hire some of their employees to conduct either action research which focus on on-going problems or Strategic research which concentrates on the issues of a long-term goals and marketing strategies. Often, this type of research is limited by what data is relatively easily available. We need to gather evidence that answers important questions about effectiveness and efficiency rather than just what is easily counted or has always been counted.

Experimental designs are of considerable importance in the organizational research.

ii) **Curiosity**

Curiosity is a crucial part of the human condition. Many professionals, including scientists, want to know more about something that interests them. There is an excitement in the discovery of new information and knowing more about some topic than anyone else. There is joy in sharing newly gathered and previously unavailable information. Finally, publishing or sharing information via publication or public meetings provides visibility and recognition. These and many more like these would lead to individual research.

iii) **Idealistic approach**

In an ideal world, research methods would be an integral part of thoughtful management of any subject development. Better reporting would result in better developments in the subject which would result in better decisions and a much more effective, visibly so, services to the community.

4 **Educational and Professional Benefits of a Re-search Degree**

An awareness of the education and skills that you develop during your research will be invaluable when you finish your research and begin the next stage of your career. Following sections highlights some of the benefits of PhD degree.

i) **Transformative Experience**

The education is an experience of personal transformation, although the nature of the transformation varies considerably and may be intensely personal. Examples that of PhD degrees providing such personal transformations include gaining a qualification, learning and developing new skill, improving employment opportunities, professional development, personal development, the pursuit of a challenge, the pleasure of learning and the advancement of knowledge. Of course, these examples are neither exhaustive nor mutually exclusive.

ii) **Specialisation in Knowledge and Skills**

Traditionally, one should develop specialization in knowledge and skill developed during the PhD.

Nevertheless, the reality nowadays is that many PhD graduates do not continue research or academia, but enter quite different careers where they are highly successful due to the confidence and training they obtained during their research programmes. Therefore, it should be obvious that the completion of doctoral research endows the student with more than heaving degree.

iii) **Transferable Skills**

The completion of PhD degree demonstrates ability to sustain application to a research project for a substantial period of time and apply a variety of management and communication skills to an original piece of research. This should also indicate ability to successfully manage a project; to identify and resolve problems; to demonstrate initiative and determination; and to communicate to a high standard. Interviews with doctoral graduates indicated that, in their opinion, one of the most important outcomes from the PhD process is the training and development of practical and intellectual skills as much as the original contribution to knowledge from their research.

5 **Points to ponder**

A number of factors affect the success or failure of research, irrespective of the method that is being used:

- **Need for research**

Topic that you are looking for must have a significant need for the research. The results need not have immediate application but the topic should not be trivial. The need to understand the nature of some specific phenomenon is the motivation for much research that has no immediate practical relevance, but there should, at the same time, be some need, importance or significance in knowing the results.

- **Research problem definition**

If you don't understand your research problem clearly then it is unlikely that you will arrive at a reasonable solution. This is an obvious remark. However, many research projects do little more than re-express a problem in a form that can then be addressed by subsequent research.

- **Research context**

There must be well-defined research context. If not, there is a danger that you will "re-invent the spoon" if you do not have a good grasp of previous work in the area. Today we are well provided with web-based search engines, advice and encouragement. It is critical that you spend some time consulting many sources before starting any research project. However, many research projects actively seek to replicate the results of previous investigations. This must be an explicit objective of your research and not an unfortunate product of poor planning.

- **Proper documentation**

It is important that you spend some time documenting your daily activities when engaged on a research project. But you should be aware that the most research is conducted under time pressure, you only have three to four years for most PhD works and two years for an MS (research), you cannot afford to waste time looking for such lost resources.

- **Time management**

Research is labour intensive. It takes time to find reference material. It can take days, weeks or months due to which you should run out of time if you do not carefully plan your allocation of time to each of these components.

- **Choose the topic of your interest and capabilities**

The research topic should match both your interests and capabilities. This will sustain you in times of frustration and offset the possibility of entering areas in which you are less competent.

- **Area for professional development**

Your PhD thesis may often be only the beginning of research on a topic. Candi-dates can make their thesis a stepping-stone in their careers by selecting a topic that provides development in areas in which they hope to work.

- **Contribution of knowledge**

The definition of this concept is difficult. A Masters research thesis does not have to make a significant contribution to knowledge. Thus it does not have to be entirely original, yet it should be based on a significant problem, research question or hypothesis. For example, you may replicate a study in a new geographical area, or with improved data and/or techniques. Your work should relate to, explain, solve or add proof to the question, problem or hypothesis. The results of your research should increase knowledge of that particular field of enquiry. Knowledge can be increased by the following.

- New or improved evidence
- New or improved methodology
- New or improved analysis
- New or improved concepts of theories

6 **Planning of the research proposal**

It is crucial that the research proposal is clear and well-planned if effort is not to be misdirected. A great deal of planning must go into your research project; possibly as much as 50 percent of the total time you spend on your thesis will be taken up by planning. The research proposal is designed to enhance your skills in the following areas:

1. Formulation of a research question.
2. Identification of a "gap" in the research literature.

3. Formulation of a set of hypotheses.
4. Preparation of a literature review pertinent to the hypotheses.
5. Choice of a methodology that is appropriate to an examination of the hypotheses.
6. Choice of techniques that are appropriate to an examination of the hypotheses.
7. Description and justification of the chosen methodology and analysis.
8. Organisation and presentation of material into a logical, clear, convincing statement of the proposed research.

7 **Organising your thesis**

Organise the research material in a logical way. There is no set structure exists but the following arrangement will fit most studies.

- **Abstract**

Summarises what your research work and how you have done it as well as the main conclusions you have drawn.

- **Chapter 1: Introduction**

Include a brief statement of the problem, question or hypotheses, the methodology used, the importance of the research, the limitations and key assumptions and the contribution to knowledge. Briefly describe the layout of your thesis by mentioning what you will do in subsequent chapters.

- **Review of related literature**

Present the theoretical foundations of the study, including a statement of research paradigm. Critically review the literature related to your topic. Move logically in the direction of a statement of your research question.

- **Chapter 3: The Research Problem Definition**

Give a comprehensive account of your research problem. Define the research model, and testable hypotheses or objectives. These hypotheses should be supported by your literature study and a brief rationale for each should be provided. This chapter may not be necessary if a comprehensive account of the research problem has been given at the end of chapter 2.

- **Chapter 4: Research Methods**

In this chapter discuss the research methods and techniques that you will employ. Give special attention (where appropriate) to your sample, measuring instruments and any statistical analysis that you will undertake.

- **Chapter 5: Research Results**

Describe simulation, analytical, experimental results, whichever you have obtained and interpret them in detail. Do not refer to other studies at this stage. In this chapter, you can also, discuss the outcomes of your study with reference to other relevant research and the underlying theoretical framework.

- **Chapter 6: Conclusions and Discussion**

Summarise your investigation and critically discuss your main findings, including limitations. Make recommendations and suggest areas for further research (if appropriate).

- **References**

A reference describes a document from which you have obtained some of your information or evidence. Citing a reference means acknowledging within your text the document from which you have obtained your information.

Why reference?

Referencing is a way of demonstrating that you have done that reading. Each time you use someone else ideas or words it is essential that you acknowledge this in your work. Not acknowledging other people's work

is not only intellectually dishonest but also illegal. You should provide references:

- To acknowledge your sources.
- To substantiate your arguments.
- To avoid plagiarism, even when unintentional.
- To enable your reader to follow up your source material.

When to reference?

Whenever you use any source of information for:

- Your inspiration.
- Particular facts, theories, findings or ideas in an author's work.
- Specific data or statistics.
- A direct quotation.
- Paraphrasing an author's words.

Where and how to reference?

There are a variety of accepted conventions for citing bibliographic references.

Several of these are set out in the British Standards BS 1629:1989 and BS5605:1990.

Please check with your research guide which method he/she wants to use.

Remember, whatever referencing method you use, references should be correct, complete and consistent, with the individual elements clearly differentiated.

- **Appendices**

An appendix is supplementary back matter or other written material added at the end of a Thesis or a book or an article or a document or any other text which is in the printed form. The purpose of appendices is basically to explain the statistical concepts or bibliographical references which are used as sources in the book or document or article. In anatomical terminology, the word appendices refers to process or projections. Here are some examples of an appendix:

- Explanations and helpful information the author has decided not to make part of the text.
- Definitions of words or concepts used in the publication.

– Maps, charts, tables, lists, diagrams, or other explanatory sections.

8 Conclusions

This article highlighted the importance and nature of research, and its benefits for personal development. It also gives some points to be followed for doing quality research. Finally, it illustrated some tips for the selection of a research problem and organisation of your Thesis.

References: -

- Åkerlind, Gerlese S. (2005) “Variation and commonality in phenomenographic research methods.” *Higher Education Research and Development* 24 (4): 321-334.
- Brew, Angela (2001) “Conceptions of research: A phenomenographic study.” *Studies in Higher Education* 26: 271–85.
- Brew, Angela and Phillis Frank (n.d.) “How is research changing? Conceptions of successful researchers.” *Research and Development in Higher Education. Advancing International Perspectives*: 131-135. Retrieved October, 2009
- Britt, Michael A. (1995) “Research on trial: A pedagogy for research methods instruction.” Paper presented at the conference *In Teaching of Psychology: Ideas and Innovations. Proceedings of the Annual Conference on Undergraduate Teaching of Psychology*. March 22-24, Ellenville, New York..
- Creswell, J. (2002) *Educational Research: Planning, Conducting and Evaluating*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Education.
- Marton, Ference and Svensson, Lennart (1979) “Conceptions of research in student learning.” *Higher Education* 8: 471-486.
- Vermunt, Jan D. (2005) “Conceptions of research and methodology learning: a commentary on the special issue.” *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research* 49 (3): 329-334.
- Woody, Robert (2004) “Misconceptions about scientific research in music education.” *Teaching Music* 11 (5).